

Article Title: **Ecological drivers of garden dormouse (*Eliomys quercinus*) occupancy in a human modified landscape in Germany**

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Fig. S1 Typical habitats of the garden dormouse in the study area in the western Harz Mountains (Photos by Hanna Liesenfelder).

Fig. S2 Representative areas of deforestation in the study area in the western Harz Mountains. Left: Fresh clear cut; Right: Typical area showing the extent of deforestation (Photos by Hanna Liesenfelder)

Fig. S3 Areas with soil removal in the study area in the western Harz Mountains (Photos by Hanna Liesenfelder)

Fig. S4 Deadwood structures in the study area in the western Harz Mountains (Photos by Hanna Liesenfelder)

Fig. S5 Successional stages in the study area in the western Harz Mountains. Succession 0: Shortly after deforestation and soil removal, high percentage of soil surface exposure, *Lythrum salicaria* as first vegetation (top left); Succession 1: Nearly no soil surface exposure, vegetation dominated by grasses (top right); Succession 2: Shrubby vegetation (often *Rubus fruticosus* and *Rubus idaeus*) starts dominating herb layer (bottom left); Succession 3: Shrubby vegetation dominates herb layer, smaller trees (*Betula* and *Picea*) emerge (bottom right) (Photos by Hanna Liesenfelder)

Fig. S6 Build-up of a footprint tunnel with cardboard and ink pad with charcoal ink (top left and right) and the placement of footprint tunnels on trees (middle left), in shrubby vegetation (middle right) and on available branches (down left and right).

Fig. S7 A typical footprint of Garden dormouse (on top) and hazel dormouse (below)

